

Web crippling design of stainless-steel sigma sections - One flange load cases

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ABSTRACT

Stainless steel sections are one of the emerging steel sections in the industry considering their benefits such as good strength, corrosion resistance, toughness and fully recyclable. The demand for stainless steel is increasing across the world as it provides the required structural capacity and considerable sustainability. Hence, research studies have been ongoing to explore latest trends in stainless steel sections. Several innovative section profiles made of stainless steel have been investigated for their structural behaviours. Similarly, sigma sections were introduced as a modification of the conventional lipped channel section in the Cold-Formed (CF) steel industry and the investigations are ongoing. However, CF Stainless Steel (CFSS) sigma sections have not been under investigation yet, which has the potential of effective structural capacity. However, CF sections are vulnerable to web crippling due to its section profile such as higher depth to thickness and width to thickness ratio. Hence, this research paper focuses on the web crippling design of CFSS sigma sections under one flange load cases. Comprehensive numerical study was conducted by employing ABAQUS/CAE after successful evaluation of numerical approach with the existing experimental data. Overall, 432 numerical models were analysed with their critical parameters such as section depth, thickness, yield strength, radius and bearing length. The results were compared with the predictions of existing design provisions. Since the design provisions fail to accurately predict the web crippling capacity of CFSS sigma sections, new modified design provisions were proposed and recommended for the prediction of web crippling capacity of CFSS sigma sections.

Keywords: Web crippling, Stainless steel, sigma sections and Numerical analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cold Formed (CF) stainless steel sections offer numerous benefits in terms of sustainability merits, corrosion resistance, enhanced durability, retained strength at elevated temperatures, aesthetic aspects, ease of fabrication, and high strength. Hence, CF stainless steel sections have emerged in the past decade, especially in modular constructions and constructions under aggressive conditions including marine environments. Stainless steel sections are being acknowledged by the industry to attain certain requirements. Researches have been ongoing on stainless steel sections based on their performance under bending, shear and web crippling. In addition, the introduction of new section profiles such as Lipped Channel Beam (LCB), unlipped channel sections, Sigma sections and SupaCee sections in stainless steel industry could be effective. Fig. 1 illustrates the section profiles of LCB, unlipped channel, SupaCee and sigma sections. However, CF section has the vulnerability of web crippling under concentrated loads due to thin cross sections. Web crippling failures can be categorized in to four load cases based on the AISI S100 (1): (1) End Two Flange (ETF); (2)

Interior Two Flange (ITF); (3) End One Flange (EOF) and (4) Interior One Flange (IOF). Fig. 2 displays the web crippling experiment setup for all load cases.

(a) Unlippped channel beam (2)

(b) LCB (Lipped Channel Beam) (3)

(c) SupaCee (4)

(d) Sigma (5)

Fig. 1. CF section profiles

Fig. 2. Load cases for the web crippling test

Web crippling behaviour of different stainless-steel sections has been investigated. On that note, Korvink et al. (6) conducted experiments on LCB sections to study the web crippling behaviour and

examined the validity of existing standard equations. Zhou and Young (7) investigated the web crippling behaviour of stainless-steel tubular sections under all four load cases and proposed design equations to predict the web crippling capacity of stainless-steel tubular sections. Li and Young (8) performed experimental and numerical program on CF ferritic stainless-steel sections to investigate the web crippling performance under all four load cases and proposed modified design equations to predict the ultimate web crippling capacity of stainless-steel sections. Yousefi et al. (9) carried out experimental and numerical investigations on CF austenitic stainless steel unlippped channel sections regarding web crippling performance under all four loading conditions and new design equations were proposed to predict the web crippling capacity of CF stainless steel unlippped channel sections.

Sigma sections are one of the innovative sections introduced in the industry to enhance the structural efficiency of stainless-steel sections. Sigma sections offer higher stiffness, enhanced load carrying ability, higher torsional rigidity, and improved resistance to distortional and local buckling. However, web crippling behaviour of sigma sections has to be analysed to employ the sections under concentrated loads. Hence, this paper intends to analyse the web crippling behaviour of stainless-steel sigma sections under one flange load cases.

2 NUMERICAL MODELLING

2.1 Element and mesh scheme

This paper presents a comprehensive numerical analysis on the web crippling behaviour of CF stainless steel sigma section under one flange load cases. Finite Element Modelling (FEM) and Analysis (FEA) software package, ABAQUS CAE, 2017, was employed in this research to model the sections and conduct the analysis. Sigma sections were modelled as a deformable shell section whereas bearing plates were modelled as rigid plates. Corner regions of the sigma sections were developed with the finer mesh of 1 mm x 5 mm to ensure a smooth loading transmission to web from flanges. Coarser mesh size of 5 mm x 5 mm was opted for flat sections of sigma and 10 mm x 10 mm mesh size for bearing plates and web side plates. The sigma section, web side plates and bearing plates were assigned and assembled according to the IOF and EOF experiment conditions. Fig. 3 depicts the assembled sigma section.

Fig. 3. Numerical model description

2.2 Material modelling

In terms of material properties of sigma section, density value of $7850 \times 10^{-12} \text{ kg/m}^3$ and elastic modulus value of 210,000 MPa were opted in the numerical model. Poisson’s ratio was selected as 0.3 and stress-strain properties of stainless-steel sigma sections were assigned based on the two-stage modified Ramberg-Osgood model which was proposed by Arrayago et al. (11) and successfully employed in previous researches (12-14) to represent the material behaviour of stainless-steel sections.

2.3 Boundary conditions

Bearing plates were assembled and connected to the flanges of stainless-steel sigma sections utilizing the surface-to-surface contact option in the ABAQUS. The FE model employed ‘Hard’ contact method to represent the interaction between rigid plates and flanges. Rigid plate surfaces were considered as master surface whereas the flanges were considered as slave surface. Contact properties were assigned to replicate the actual experiment conditions. Hence, a frictional coefficient was set between the surfaces using the kinematic contact finite sliding method. Fig. 4 indicates the applied contact properties.

Fig. 4. Applied contact properties.

Reference points were created in bearing plates to assign the boundary conditions and Figure 4 presents the details of the boundary conditions regarding translational (U_x , U_y and U_z) and rotational degree of freedoms (UR_x , UR_y and UR_z). In both bearing plates, rotational degree of freedom with respect to X-axis (UR_x) was set free and translational degree of freedom with respect to Y-axis (U_y) was set as 20 mm downwards. This method was employed in similar previous research (15-17). Fig. 5 illustrates the boundary conditions.

Fig. 5. Boundary condition configurations for the analysis

2.4 Analysis methods

ABAQUS/Explicit solver method was opted to carry out the numerical analysis which is suitable due to its efficiency especially in three-dimensional analysis, lesser computational requirement, and the greater ability to rectify the issues related material deformations. ABAQUS/standard solver method is a similar method which can be applicable in web crippling numerical analysis. However, it was overlooked due to its convergence issues. Hence, ABAQUS/Explicit method was utilized in the study based on the similar past similar web crippling studies (12-21).

3 VALIDATION AND PARAMETRIC PLAN

3.1 Validation

Numerical based investigations require proper verification of developed numerical models to establish that the results from the investigation are reliable. Hence, in this study the numerical models were checked with experiment studies to prove their credibility of replicating actual experimental conditions. Experimental studies conducted by Yousefi et al. (9) on stainless steel LCB sections under one flange load cases were taken into consideration for the validation of numerical models. The validation process includes the comparisons of failure pattern of numerical model and tested beam specimen, the load vs displacement curve from the numerical study and experiment and the ultimate capacities from numerical model and tested beams. Table 1 presents the validation results and Fig. 6 illustrates the failure pattern comparison.

Fig. 6. Failure pattern comparison

Table 1. Validation results

Specimen	Bearing Length, l_b (mm)	Test (kN)	FE-Model (kN)	Test / FE- Model
IOF load case				
175 × 60-t1.5-B50-A0-FU	50	10.16	10.21	1.00
175 × 60-t1.5-B75-A0-FU	75	11.32	11.24	1.01
175 × 60-t1.5-B100-A0-FU	100	12.2	12.55	0.97
200 × 75-t1.5-B50-A0-FU	50	9.96	9.05	1.10
200 × 75-t1.5-B75-A0-FU	75	11.27	11.87	0.95
200 × 75-t1.5-B100-A0-FU	100	12.4	12.64	0.98
Mean				1.00
COV				0.05
EOF load case				
Section	Bearing Length, l_b (mm)	Test (kN)	FE-Model (kN)	Test/FE Model
175 × 60-t1.5-B50-A0	50	4.54	4.68	0.97
175 × 60-t1.5-B75-A0	75	4.95	4.88	1.01
200 × 75-t1.5-B50-A0	50	4.35	4.5	0.97
200 × 75-t1.5-B100-A0	100	5.06	5.02	1.01
250 × 75-t1.5-B75-A0	75	4.03	3.87	1.04
250 × 75-t1.5-B100-A0	100	4.34	4.11	1.06
Mean				1.01
COV				0.04

3.2 Parametric plan

Based on the validation, the numerical approach was opted to conduct the numerical analysis of stainless-steel sigma sections under one flange load cases. From the literature review, critical parameters were identified and included in the parametric plan and their range was set considering the industry demands. Table 2 states the parametric plan with the total number of models of 216. Parametric plan comprises 4 different section depths (140 mm, 200 mm, 240 mm, and 300 mm), 3 various thicknesses and radii (1 mm, 2 mm, and 3 mm) and (3 mm, 5 mm, and 7 mm), 2 different yield strengths (220 MPa and 450 MPa) and 3 bearing lengths (50 mm, 100 mm, and 150 mm). Comprehensive FEA was conducted based on the parametric plan and results were obtained.

Table 2. Parametric plan

Material	Section depth (mm)	Thickness	Bearing length	Radius	Yield strength	No. of Models
		(mm)	(mm)	(mm)	(MPa)	
CF stainless- steel	140, 200, 240, 300	1,2,3	50,100,150	3, 5, 7	220,450	216
Both IOF and EOF load cases						216 x 2
Total numerical models						432

4 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

After the comprehensive numerical analysis of stainless-steel sigma sections under one flange load cases, the results were combined and stated in Table 3 and Table 4. The results were compared with critical parameters and their impacts were compared. The failure pattern is illustrated under both load cases in Fig. 7, and it indicates that thickness, bearing length and yield strength made a positive impact on web crippling capacity of stainless-steel sigma section under one flange load cases whereas section depth and radius made a negative impact on web crippling strength of stainless-steel sigma sections while they were increased.

(a) EOF load case

(b) IOF load case

Fig. 7. Failure pattern of sigma section

Table. 3. Results obtained from numerical studies for sections 140 mm and 200 mm

t (mm)	l _b (mm)	r (mm)	Section depth (mm)			
			140		200	
			Yield strength (MPa)			
			220	450	220	450
IOF load case, Web crippling capacity (kN)						
1	50	3	4.21	7.54	3.92	7.02
1	50	5	4.13	7.45	3.83	6.7
1	50	7	4.01	7.39	3.75	6.52
1	100	3	4.96	7.93	4.73	7.33
1	100	5	4.6	7.72	4.23	7.2
1	100	7	4.39	7.58	4.13	7.01
1	150	3	5.49	8.39	5.29	7.95
1	150	5	4.84	8.07	4.71	7.85
1	150	7	4.47	7.93	4.4	7.74
2	50	3	13.49	22.79	13.04	21.66
2	50	5	13.29	22.52	12.81	21.15
2	50	7	13.03	22.46	12.58	20.99
2	100	3	15.28	25.85	14.69	24.49
2	100	5	14.35	24.81	13.7	24.29
2	100	7	13.66	23.86	13.34	23.37
2	150	3	16.96	28.06	16.45	27.2
2	150	5	16.04	27.45	15.52	26.34
2	150	7	14.92	25.94	14.55	25.59
3	50	3	29.2	45.49	26.25	43.36
3	50	5	26.9	44.3	25.75	41.94
3	50	7	24.86	43.62	24.37	41.6
3	100	3	30.47	52.13	28.58	48.7
3	100	5	28.42	49.32	27.22	47.67
3	100	7	26.97	47.61	26.2	47.06
3	150	3	33.58	57.44	31.43	53.36

3	150	5	31.65	53.13	29.86	51.72
3	150	7	29.41	51.02	28.52	50.23
			EOF load case			
1	50	3	1.88	3.2	1.63	2.55
1	50	5	1.73	3.01	1.53	2.41
1	50	7	1.68	2.84	1.46	2.28
1	100	3	2.32	3.38	1.94	3.1
1	100	5	2.08	3.15	1.94	2.97
1	100	7	1.88	2.99	1.69	2.81
1	150	3	2.67	4.62	2.3	3.83
1	150	5	2.38	3.48	2.14	3.63
1	150	7	2.17	3.29	1.97	3.35
2	50	3	6.28	10.17	5.72	9.11
2	50	5	6.15	9.99	5.41	8.5
2	50	7	5.2	8.83	4.88	7.96
2	100	3	7.99	12.71	6.96	11.05
2	100	5	7.04	11	6.42	9.97
2	100	7	6.33	11.25	5.83	9.27
2	150	3	9.2	15.44	8.3	13.04
2	150	5	8.73	13.98	7.9	11.98
2	150	7	7.53	12.09	6.92	10.93
3	50	3	12.5	21	11.61	19.11
3	50	5	11.25	19.67	10.56	17.67
3	50	7	10.53	18.15	9.89	16.54
3	100	3	15.81	28.33	14.51	24.79
3	100	5	14.97	26.99	13.42	22.58
3	100	7	12.93	22.21	12.22	20.93
3	150	3	19.13	33	17.14	29.79
3	150	5	18.41	30.27	16.54	26.71
3	150	7	16.09	26.26	15.31	24.12

Table. 4. Results obtained from numerical studies for sections 240 mm and 300 mm

t (mm)	l _b (mm)	r (mm)	Section depth (mm)			
			240		300	
			Yield strength (MPa)			
			220	450	220	450
			IOF load case, Web crippling capacity (kN)			
1	50	3	3.85	6.14	3.56	5.5
1	50	5	3.75	5.84	3.13	4.74
1	50	7	3.64	5.78	3.02	4.54
1	100	3	4.62	7.25	4.3	6.44
1	100	5	4.14	7.09	3.91	5.77
1	100	7	3.95	6.78	3.62	5.36
1	150	3	5.18	7.83	4.8	7.11
1	150	5	4.64	7.69	4.36	6.52
1	150	7	4.24	7.48	3.99	6.07
2	50	3	12.73	21.13	11.62	18.28
2	50	5	11.97	20.66	10.45	16.65
2	50	7	11.22	20.27	9.85	15.86

2	100	3	14.23	24.01	13.74	21.17
2	100	5	13.42	23.58	12.69	20.18
2	100	7	13.09	23.07	11.92	18.79
2	150	3	16.14	26.28	15.6	23.4
2	150	5	15.05	25.9	14.37	21.94
2	150	7	14.06	25.25	13.43	20.64
3	50	3	25.5	43.13	22.74	37.26
3	50	5	24.02	41.5	22.06	35.28
3	50	7	23.75	40.79	20.11	33.52
3	100	3	28.25	48.39	26.86	43.03
3	100	5	27.04	47.37	25.33	40.63
3	100	7	25.48	46.19	24	39.4
3	150	3	30.71	52.41	30.24	47.47
3	150	5	29.52	51.23	28.53	44.75
3	150	7	28.13	49.65	26.91	44
EOF load case						
1	50	3	1.58	2.33	1.48	2.18
1	50	5	1.51	2.21	1.44	2.08
1	50	7	1.45	2.18	1.42	2.01
1	100	3	1.88	2.99	1.81	2.71
1	100	5	1.76	2.83	1.61	2.57
1	100	7	1.63	2.58	1.58	2.41
1	150	3	2.2	3.51	2.16	3.29
1	150	5	2.02	3.35	1.78	3.11
1	150	7	1.89	3.2	1.74	2.99
2	50	3	5.66	9.03	5.07	8.35
2	50	5	5.3	8.45	5.01	8.05
2	50	7	4.79	7.85	4.6	7.82
2	100	3	6.86	10.92	5.79	9.23
2	100	5	6.32	9.93	5.57	8.72
2	100	7	5.71	9.21	5.34	8.35
2	150	3	7.97	12.85	6.89	10.18
2	150	5	7.57	12.17	6.56	9.73
2	150	7	6.75	10.89	6.14	9.21
3	50	3	11.31	18.88	10.37	18.02
3	50	5	10.51	17.59	10.04	17.25
3	50	7	9.7	16.38	9.56	15.59
3	100	3	14.17	23.99	12.13	20.7
3	100	5	13.07	21.65	11.75	19.7
3	100	7	11.73	19.97	11.29	18.72
3	150	3	16.97	28.64	14.29	23.85
3	150	5	15.84	23.39	13.64	22.41
3	150	7	14.44	22.4	13.68	21.38

5 DESIGN PROVISIONS

AS/NZS 4673 (22) provides the design specifications for stainless steel sections to predict their web crippling capacity. Accordingly, Eq. 1 and 2 are provided in the AS/NZS 4673 (21) to predict the

web crippling capacity of stainless-steel sections under EOF and IOF load cases. In addition, EN-1993-1-3 (23) provides the web crippling equations (Eq. 3 and 4) for CF steel sections under one flange load cases.

$$P_{AS/NZS\ 4673} = C_3 C_4 C_\theta t^2 (1.51 - 0.002 d_1/t) (1 + 0.01 N/t) \quad \text{EOF load case} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{AS/NZS\ 4673} = C_1 C_2 C_\theta t^2 (3.71 - 0.005 d_1/t) (1 + 0.007 N/t) \quad \text{IOF load case} \quad (2)$$

Where: $C_1 = (1.22 - 0.22k)k$; $C_2 = (1.06 - 0.06 r/t)$; $C_3 = (1.33 - 0.33k)k$; $C_4 = (1.15 - 0.15 r/t)$ $C_\theta = 0.7 + 0.3 (\varphi / 90)^2$; $k = f_y/228$; t-thickness; d_1 - depth of the flat portion; r - radius and N- bearing length.

$$R_{w,Rd} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 t^2 f_{yb} (5.92 - \frac{h_w}{132t}) (1 + 0.01 \frac{N}{t})}{\gamma_{M1}} \quad \text{EOF load case} \quad (3)$$

$$R_b = k_3 k_4 k_5 \left(14.7 - \frac{h/t}{49.5} \right) \left(1 + 0.007 \frac{N}{t} \right) t^2 f_y \quad \text{IOF load case} \quad N/t \leq 60: \quad (4)$$

$$R_b = k_3 k_4 k_5 \left(14.7 - \frac{h/t}{49.5} \right) \left(0.75 + 0.011 \frac{N}{t} \right) t^2 f_y \quad \text{IOF load case} \quad N/t > 60 \quad (5)$$

Where: $k_1 = 1.33 - 0.33 \frac{f_{yb}}{228}$; $k_2 = (1.15 - 0.15 r/t)$; $k_3 = 0.7 + 0.3 (\varphi / 90)^2$; $k = f_y/228$, $k_4 = 1.22 - 0.22k$, $k_5 = 1.06 - 0.06 (\frac{r}{t})$, f_y - yield strength; t- thickness; h_w - web height between flange mid lines; N- bearing length and $\gamma_{M1}=1$.

Obtained numerical results were compared with design provisions of AS/NZS 4673 (22) and EN-1993-1-3 (23). Since, the comparison indicated the ineffectiveness design provisions and modified design provisions of EN-1993-1-3 (23) were proposed. Reliability analysis was carried out for proposed equations and the resistance factor (ϕ_w) of 0.88 was proposed for proposed modifications. Table 5 presents the proposed modifications. Fig. 8 illustrates the comparison of FE results the predictions of proposed modifications.

Table 5. Proposed coefficients for proposed equations

Load case	K_3	K_1/ K_4	K_2/ K_5	Mean	COV	ϕ_w
IOF	$0.7+0.3 (\varphi/90)^2$	$0.027 - 0.02 f_y/1170$	$49.0 - 0.01 \frac{r}{t}$	1.00	0.09	0.88
EOF		$0.86 - 0.16 f_y/228$	$1.40 - 0.02 \frac{r}{t}$	1.00	0.11	0.88

Fig. 8. Comparison of FE results with the proposed equation

6 CONCLUSION

This paper presents a comprehensive numerical analysis on web crippling performance of CF stainless steel sigma sections under one flange load cases. Numerical models were developed according to the industry standards of sigma sections, and they were validated with experimental studies. Since the validation was satisfactory, the parametric plan was developed to analyse the web crippling behaviour of stainless-steel sigma sections under one flange load cases comprising different values of critical parameters such as section depth, thickness, radius, bearing length and yield strength. A proper parametric plan was structured consisting of 432 models and the numerical simulations were carried out using the FEA software, ABAQUS CAE, 2017. The results were obtained and compared with critical parameters and existing design codes. Design equations were modified to accurately predict the web crippling capacity under one flange load cases. This research recommends employing the stainless-steel sections in appropriate places in the industry more often to utilize its structural potentials as well as sustainability merits.

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